

Proposed method for measuring the speed of light in one direction.

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Summary:

This work addresses the conceptual difficulty of measuring the speed of light in one direction, which requires remotely synchronized clocks, but whose synchronization depends on the behavior of light itself. An alternative experimental method is proposed that uses two clocks synchronized by a pressure wave in a controlled tube, allowing the measurement of the travel time of a unidirectional light beam. By employing mechanical signals with a speed much lower than that of light, relativistic effects and electronic delays are eliminated, guaranteeing operational synchronization independent of the optical channel. The procedure does not replace Einstein's convention but offers an explicit protocol for mechanical synchronization, providing a unidirectional measurement of light referenced to this time frame.

Introduction:

Measuring the speed of light in a single spatial direction presents a well-known conceptual difficulty: from a emitting point to a distant receiver without a round trip. This requires perfectly synchronized clocks in separate locations, but any long-distance synchronization procedure already depends on assumptions about how light propagates, introducing an unavoidable circularity into the measurement. For this reason, the directly experimentally accessible quantity is the speed of light along a closed path, while the equality of the speed in all directions is adopted as an operational convention. This convention was explicitly formulated by Albert Einstein in 1905 when establishing the clock synchronization method of special relativity, and was metrologically consolidated when the General Conference on Weights and Measures redefined the meter in 1983, precisely setting the value of c at 299,792,458 m/s.

Proposed method:

Based on the problems identified so far, a method is proposed consisting of a system with two clocks to be synchronized: Clock 1 (R1) and Clock 2 (R2).

The synchronization of the clocks, which will measure the time it takes for light to travel from one end to the other over a known distance d , will be achieved by means of a straight tube with a smooth interior and constant diameter; under controlled pressure, humidity, and temperature, through which a pressure wave will circulate:

The pressure wave will be emitted from R1 a known time before the light beam to be measured is emitted.

This time must be greater than:

$$d / 299,792,458 \text{ m/s}$$

(Ideally twice the time or more to allow for a margin in the measurement)

At time 0, when R1 emits the pressure wave, R1 will begin counting, while R2 will begin counting when the pressure wave reaches it.

It is important to note that the distance d between the tubes through which the light beam to be measured travels and the pressure wave must be identical.

Once both clocks are running, with a counting difference related to the speed of sound in the tube, both clocks will be synchronized according to the adopted mechanical protocol. It is at this point that the light beam can be emitted to perform the measurement in one direction only:

The beam will be emitted from R1, stopping it; and upon reaching R2, it will stop it. The difference between the readings of both clocks, minus the initial difference due to the pressure wave's velocity, will allow us to obtain the operational value of the unidirectional speed of the light beam under the defined mechanical synchronization.

It is important to note that for the pressure wave, the speed, time, and synchronization scales involved are enormous compared to relativistic effects. They are completely negligible: If we compare:

Speed of sound in air $\approx 340 \text{ m/s}$

Speed of light $\approx 300,000,000 \text{ m/s}$

Relationship:

$$\frac{v_{\text{sonido}}}{c} \approx 10^{-6}$$

Relativistic effects appear when speeds are a significant fraction of the speed of light.

The relativistic factor:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

For the sound:

$$\gamma \approx 1 + 5 \times 10^{-13}$$

This is far below the capabilities of any normal experimental measurement.

In measuring the time taken by a pressure wave, the following example demonstrates that the same clock can be used to determine the propagation speed:

Emitter A —cable— oscilloscope

Microphone B —cable— oscilloscope

Sound takes on the order of milliseconds, while the electrical signal takes on the order of nanoseconds.

There is no synchronization ambiguity.

Since the speed of the pressure wave is several orders of magnitude less than c , relativistic effects and electronic delays are negligible compared to the instrumental time resolution.

It is important to note that: both clocks are at relative rest; they share physical conditions, they have the same time scale, they are synchronized by a real physical signal (pressure wave), there is no relativistic clock transport, there are no moving frames, and there are no time dilation paradoxes. The final measurement will be taken with the clocks stopped. This means there are no digital signals traveling from each clock to a central information hub, nor any additional components that would increase the system's complexity..

Scope of the method:

This procedure does not aim to replace the light synchronization convention of special relativity formulated by Albert Einstein, but rather to explicitly define an alternative synchronization protocol based on a mechanical signal. Consequently, the value obtained corresponds to an operational unidirectional measurement referred to this temporal protocol, allowing for experimental analysis of the measurement's dependence on the physical synchronization channel used. It provides an operational unidirectional measurement of light propagation based on mechanical synchronization, independent of the optical channel, and explicitly states the temporal convention employed.

This document should be considered a theoretical article that may eventually offer a relatively unexplored approach and lead to potential experiments.